

THE IMPORTANCE OF SEGMENTATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

Abdullabekova Noilaxon G`ofurjon qizi

Namangan State University Faculty of Economics, 3rd Stage Student

Namangan, Uzbekistan

E-mail: abdullabekova202n@gmail.com

Abstract: This article shows the importance and effectiveness of segmenting the population in the development of the tourism sector, through which the provision of targeted tourist services is established. The effectiveness of the application of marketing strategies for the development of tourism, which is the main network in the country, has been shown.

Key words: Tourism sector, hotel business, tourist category, segmentation, marketing strategy, gross domestic product, population income, economic benefits.

The tourism industry and other service industries arise directly with the participation of members of society, and satisfying their desires is our first priority. In the theory of economics, it is known that if we are based on the law of supply and demand, the cost of products and services that are in high demand will also be high. And the growth in demand can be achieved primarily by studying the desires of consumers.

There are also different approaches to product selection as each person has a unique character. In the case of market segmentation, however, it is advisable for marketers to work and make plans with the aim of bringing profit.

The market segment is this-such an isolated part of consumers, goods, competitors, for which common features are characteristic. Proper market segmentation consists in properly organizing the supply of goods at low costs, strictly adhering to the specific needs of the same segment.³

³Ergashkhodjayeva Sh.Dj., Abdukhaliyeva L.T. Marketing research. Textbook.. - T.: Economics, 2019. 378 PP.

We can better understand the market by studying the consumer's desire. In the segmentation process, we usually divided consumers into location, behavior, demographic background, and socioeconomic groups.

"Marketing services" - the organization of the market of goods and services, and in this process, the processes of communicating goods to retail, demonstrating to sale, advertising, establishing relations with the buyer, establishing sales and organizing additional services by the manufacturer, intermediary, seller are understood, and the service consists of a set of actions carried out by the buyer (manufacturer) and consumer.⁴

As a result of research, it is also thought that the spending on segmentation will also benefit well. Our country, as we can see from natural climatic conditions, has favorable conditions for tourists, and tourist recreation facilities established in nature are being appreciated. The population is cut off from the modern globalized world and there is a desire to live in harmony with nature.

The fact that the tourism services sector is making a significant contribution to GDP and at the same time has the property of quickly recovering itself in any situation is also evidence that it is an area of sufficient importance in its place. As a result of the policy implemented in Uzbekistan, the attention paid to tourism is sufficient, and year-to-year strategies clearly show the goals set for the development of Tourism. In particular, the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy also aims to do the following things.

- To increase the number of foreign tourists to 15 million, the number of domestic tourists to 25 million, and the number of tourists coming on pilgrimage tourism to 3 million.

- To create 30 large tourist clusters in the Republic due to attracting private investment, to increase the number of guest places by at least 2 times, to build 25 door roads in mountainous areas, to increase the number of tourist neighborhoods to 175.

⁴ Uzoqov Muhibillo Juraboyevich, & Jo'raboyev Jo'rabek Muhibillo o'g'li. (2022). KORXONALARDA MARKETING XIZMATINI TASHKIL ETISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI. RESEARCH AND EDUCATION, 1(9), 371–377. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495652>

- To bring tourism services exports to \$ 5 billion, and medical and educational tourism exports to \$ 1.5 billion annually.

- Further promotion of the creation of companies that provide intercity bus service on the scale of our country.

- In total, more than 1,000 power plants, catering and recreation, trade and service points are organized.⁵

It will be necessary for the leaders of the enterprise, which was previously operating in tourism, that is, for legal entities and individuals to carry out strong strategic planning in the success of their business. The state also needs to bring a state of political stability to the development of this sphere. Through the implementation of Market Segmentation and the practical application of the proposals given, we can have the following opportunities in the hotel and tourism business:

- it will be possible to achieve effect by increasing the time of feedback with customers, taking into account that each person has his own desires, we will create a product accordingly. Increasing customer satisfaction leads to increased demand;

- it is necessary to create a flexible turpentine let it have the property of quickly adapting to a traveler from different categories and different regions. It is worth noting that for this, of course, it is necessary to constantly focus on marketing processes;

- to be more information-driven and news-driven. It embodies such basic aspects as market research, attention to the desires of the population and not repeating the shortcomings of your competitors in yourself.

List of literature used:

1. Ergashkhodjayeva Sh.Dj., Abdukhalilova L.T. Marketing research. Textbook.: Economics, 2019. 378 PP

2. Uzoqov Muhibillo Juraboyevich, & Jo‘raboyev Jo‘rabek Muhibillo o‘g‘li. (2022). KORXONALARDA MARKETING XIZMATINI TASHKIL ETISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI. RESEARCH AND EDUCATION, 1(9), 371–377. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495652>

3. Decree Of The President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan/ON THE STRATEGY "UZBEKISTAN-2030"/11.09.2023

⁵ Decree Of The President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan/ON THE STRATEGY "UZBEKISTAN-2030"/11.09.2023